

Triterpenoids from *Gynocardia odorata* and their antimicrobial activity

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Abstract : Triterpenoids, taraxerone, tricadenic acid, β -sitosterol, odolactone, acetyl odolactone, 3-O α -actyl friedelan 27 \rightarrow 15 α -olide and 3-O α -actyl friedelan 27 \rightarrow 16 α -olide were isolated from the methanol extract of the outer bark of *Gynocardia odorata* available in Darjeeling foothills. 3-O α -actyl friedelan 27 \rightarrow 15 α -olide and 3-O β -actyl friedelan 27 \rightarrow 16 α -olide are being reported for the first time isolated from this plant. The structure of these compounds was determined by means of chemical and spectral data (IR, NMR) or by comparison with authentic specimen. A preliminary study on their antimicrobial activities has also been carried out against some fungal and bacterial species.

Keywords : Triterpene, *Gynocardia odorata*, odolactone, 3-O α -actyl friedelan 27 \rightarrow 15 α -olide, 3-O α -actyl friedelan 27 \rightarrow 16 α -olide, antimicrobial.

Introduction

Prior to the year 1900 it was generally believed that the "chaulmoogra oil" of commerce was obtained from the seeds of *Gynocardia odorata* (R. Br.). The oil from the seed is used in folk medicine for its antileprotic, anti-syphilitic, antirheumatic properties in scrofula, eczema, psoriasis and gout. The bark yielded the triterpens odolactone, acetyl-odolactone, characterized as derivatives of friedelan 26-12-betalactone¹. Fruits of *Gynocardia odorata* acts as a piscicide, in ethanol were found to possess antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Trichophyton rubru*². Previous studies have revealed several bioactive triterpenoids including betulinic acid, betulin etc. In an ongoing search for bioactive triterpenoids from *Gynocardia odorata*, the ethanol extract was selected for further investigation.

Results and discussion

Out of the seven compounds isolated from the plant, five of them, e.g. taraxerone, tricadenic acid, β -sitosterol, odolactone, acetyl odolactone, were reported earlier and the structure of each of them was established on the basis of spectral data, m.p. and by comparison with the already reported data³⁻⁵. Rest two, 3-O β -actyl friedelan 27 \rightarrow 15 α -olide (**1**) and 3-O β -actyl friedelan 27 \rightarrow 16 α -olide (**2**) are reporting for the first time. The structures of both

the compounds were established based on their spectral data (IR, UV and NMR) and also by comparison with the already reported data⁵. All the compounds were evaluated for their antifungal and antibacterial activities.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. The NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ solutions at ambient temperature on a Bruker Avance 300 MHz-FT NMR spectrometer using 5 mm BBO probe. The chemical shifts δ are given in ppm related to tetra methyl silane (TMS) as internal standard. The coupling constant (*J*) are reported in Hz. The IR spectra were recorded in Shimadzu FT-IR spectrophotometer in KBr discs. Column chromatography was performed over silica gel (60-120 mesh, BDH). TLC was performed on chromatoplate of silica gel G (Glaxo and BDH) and the spots were located by exposing to iodine chamber.

Compound 1 :

White crystalline solid, m.p. > 320 °C, $[\alpha]_D -19^\circ$ (Found : C, 87.10; H, 12.09. Calcd. for C₃₂H₅₀O₄ (498) : C, 87.39; H, 12.36%); m.p. 319-320 °C (chloroform-methanol); $[\alpha]_D -18.80$; IR : 1730 and 1240 cm⁻¹ for acetoxy group and at 1750 cm⁻¹ for a γ -lactone moiety; ¹H NMR : δ 0.84 (6H), 0.96 (3H), 0.97 (3H), 1.01 (3H), 1.16 (3H) and 0.75 (3H, d, *J* 6 Hz), 2.04, 4.60 (C-3),

4.34 (geminal to the lactone oxygen) ppm. Mass : m/z 498 $[M]^+$, other peaks 439 $[M-COOCH_3]^+$, 423 $[438-CH_3]^+$, 383, 370, 316, 315, 255, 252, 218, 192, 177, 123 (base peak), 107, 95, 55. Thus from spectral analysis and by comparison (mixed m.p., Co-IR, Co-TLC, Co-NMR) with an authentic sample it has been identified as 3-O β -actyl friedelan 27 \rightarrow 15 α -olide (**1**) (Lit.⁵ m.p. 320 °C, $[\alpha]_D -19^\circ$).

Compound 2 :

White crystalline solid, compound, m.p. > 320 °C, $[\alpha]_D - 23^\circ$ (Found : C, 87.18; H, 12.17. Calcd. for C₃₂H₅₀O₄ (498) : C, 87.32; H, 12.40%); m.p. 319–320 °C (chloroform-methanol); IR : 1725 cm⁻¹ (δ -lactone moiety) and at 1740 and 1240 cm⁻¹ (acetoxy group); ¹H NMR : δ 0.82, 0.84, 0.93, 0.98, 1.19, 1.23 and 0.73 (3H, d, J 6 Hz), 2.02 (acetoxy methyl group), 4.6 (1H, ddd, J 11, 12 and 5 Hz), 3.98 (J 3 Hz), C-26 (appeared at 1.23) and C-28 (appeared at 1.25) methyls in comparison to that observed in deoxydolactone and in the compound, suggested the attachment of the lactone oxygen at C-16 rather than at C-15 in compound (**1**). However the PMR spectrum for the lactone part of compound was almost similar to that of deoxyisodolactone. ¹H NMR data of the compound is presented along with that of compound (**1**) in Table 4. Mass : (m/z 498), other peaks at 439 $[M-COOCH_3]^+$, 438 $[M-CH_3COOH]^+$, 423 $[438-CH_3]^+$, 383, 382, 370, 355, 315, 314 (base peak), 269, 255, 189, 187, 122, 109, 107, 95, 81, 69, 55. Thus from spectral analysis and by comparison (mixed m.p., Co-IR, Co-TLC, Co-NMR) with an authentic sample it has been identified as 3-O α -actyl friedelan 27 \rightarrow 16 α -olide (**2**) (Lit.⁵ m.p. 320 °C, $[\alpha]_D - 23^\circ$).

Antimicrobial activity :

Although the natural products isolated, do not show any significant phytotoxicity when tested on a number of specimens (Table 3) but all the isolated compounds showed prominent antimicrobial activities against the tested fungal and bacterial pathogens as evidenced from the Tables 1 and 2. Compound **1** and **2** showed better activity against all the microorganisms compare to the other compounds and their activity is found comparable to that of Ampicillin against *E. coli* and *Enterobacter*. The activity of compound **1** and **2** was nearly comparable to that of Bavistan, when tested against *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* and *Colletotrichum camelliae*. Finally it can be concluded that

Table 1. MICs of **1** to **7** against different bacteria

Compds.	MIC in $\mu\text{g/ml}$ against different bacterial strains			
	EC	BS	SA	EB
1	130	< 150	100	100
2	150	100	200	100
3	100	130	150	150
4	200	170	130	200
5	150	150	< 150	100
6	100	100	100	< 150
7	100	< 100	100	100
Ampicillin	128	64	64	128

BS - *Bacillus subtilis*, EC - *Escherichia coli*, SA - *Staphylococcus aureus*, EB - *Enterobacter*, MIC - Minimum inhibitory concentration.

Table 2. MICs of **1** to **7** against different fungi

Compds.	MIC in $\mu\text{g/ml}$ against different bacterial strains				
	CG	FE	CE	AA	CC
1	< 5.0	20.0	40.0	10.0	< 5.0
2	4.87	19.5	40.0	19.5	39.0
3	5.00	20.0	35.0	20.0	39.0
4	4.50	19.0	35.0	20.0	40.0
5	4.00	15.0	32.5	15.5	35.0
6	3.70	10.5	30.5	15.0	32.5
7	3.70	10.0	30.5	15.0	30.5
Bavistan	3.50	3.50	3.70	4.00	4.20

CG - *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, FE - *Fusarium equiseti*, CE - *Curvularia eragrostidis*, AA - *Alternaria alternata*, CC - *Colletotrichum camelliae*.

Table 3. Phytotoxicity of the compounds based on the length (in cm) of roots after 7 days

Compds.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Rice	Wheat	Pea
Taraxerone	Control	0.5	1.10	1.53
	100	0.5	11.2	1.53
	250	0.5	1.13	1.53
	500	0.5	1.12	1.53
Tricardenic acid	100	0.5	1.21	1.62
	250	0.5	1.22	1.64
	500	0.5	1.25	1.65
β -Sitosterol	100	0.5	1.09	1.65
	250	0.5	1.09	1.64
	500	0.5	1.11	1.63
Odolactone	100	0.6	1.32	1.62
	250	0.6	1.30	1.62
	500	0.6	1.25	1.63

Table-3 (contd.)

Acetyl odolactone	100	0.5	1.31	1.69
	250	0.5	1.30	1.70
	500	0.5	1.29	1.74
3-O α -actyl friedelan	100	0.5	1.12	1.44
	250	0.5	1.12	1.44
	500	0.5	1.12	1.46
3-O α -actyl friedelan	100	0.5	1.13	1.45
	250	0.5	1.13	1.46
	500	0.5	1.13	1.45

Table 4. Comparison of ^1H NMR chemical shifts of 3-O α -actyl friedelan 27 \rightarrow 15 α -olide (1), 3-O α -actyl friedelan 27 \rightarrow 16 α -olide (2), deoxyodolactone⁵ and deoxyisoodolactone

Assignment	Chemical shifts in ppm	
	Compound-1	Compound-2
C24-Me	0.75 (d, <i>J</i> 6.6 Hz)	0.73 (d, <i>J</i> 6.6 Hz)
C23-Me	0.84	0.82
C25-Me	0.84	0.84
C29-Me	0.96	0.93
C30-Me	0.97	0.98
C27 ^a or	1.01	1.19
C26-Me		
C28-Me	1.16	1.23
C3-H _a	4.60 (ddd, <i>J</i> 11, 12 and 5 Hz)	4.60 (ddd, <i>J</i> 11, 12 and 5 Hz)
C15-H _a	4.34 (t, <i>J</i> 3 Hz)	-
C16-H _a	-	3.98 (t, <i>J</i> 3 Hz)

^aMost likely assignment.

the present study will be extremely helpful to enrich the present knowledge about different types of triterpenoids and also help the researchers to design newer generation of drugs based on such information about triterpenoids.

General procedure :

Fresh outer bark of *G. odorata* was collected from Sukna belt of foothills of Darjeeling in an early summer. The plants collected were shade dried at room temperature and mechanically reduced to coarse powder. The prepared powdered leaves were then used for further studies. The powdered plant material (2 g) was extracted with methanol in a soxhlet apparatus for 72 h. The solvent was recovered at reduced pressure, which yielded a deep brown gummy residue (1.2 g). This crude methanol extract of the plant was then fractionated over a column of silica gel of 60–120 mesh using petroleum ether and ethyl acetate with increasing concentration as eluent.

Fig. 1. Isolated triterpenoids from *Gynocardia odorata*.

In the present study, five different fungal pathogens (*Colletotrichum camelliae*, *Fusarium equisiti*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Curvularia eragrostidis* and *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*) were used for *in vitro* antifungal assay^{6,7}. Antibacterial assay were performed against four bacterial pathogens (*Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterobacter*). Suitable strains of these organisms were procured from the microbiology laboratory of our institute. MICs (Minimum inhibitory concentration) of the triterpenoids against bacterial and fungal pathogens have been presented in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The antifungal and antibacterial media used are as follows. For nutrient agar 28 g of media (HiMedia) was suspended in 1000 ml of distilled water according to the manufacturer's protocol. It was boiled to dissolve the medium completely at sterilized by autoclaving at 15 lbs pressure (121 °C for 15 min). The nutrient agar contained peptic digest of animal tissue (5 g), sodium chloride (5 g), beef extract (1.5 g), yeast extract (1.5 g), agar (15 g) and dissolved water (1000 ml). pH was adjusted to 7.2. For preparation of PDA (potato-dextrose-agar) peeled potato was cut into small pieces and boiled in required

volume of dissolved water. The mixture was filtered through muslin cloth and the extract was mixed with dextrose and agar. The resultant mixture was heated in order to dissolve. Finally the media was sterilized at 15 lbs (121 °C for 15 min). Composition of the media was peeled potato (400 g), dextrose (20 g), agar (20 g) and dissolved water (1000 ml). pH was adjusted to 6.0. DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide) was used as solvent to prepare different concentrations of the triterpenoids. Solvent control (DMSO) was also maintained throughout the experiment. All experiments were performed in petridishes and were incubated at 37 °C for 48 h. The required media (either PDA or NA) was poured in a petridish and allowed for solidification. After solidification wells or cups were made by inserting a cork borer in the media. The numbers of wells were made according to the requirement of the experiment. Fungal spores were suspended on the PDA media before well or cup formation. Test solution (100 µL/well) was poured in the well or cup. We compared the antifungal activities of these compounds with that of Bavistan and antibacterial activity with that of Ampicillin, a β-lactam antibiotic.

Seeds of rice (*Oriza sativa*), wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) and pea (*Pisum sativum*) were collected from local market. The assay seeds were sorted for uniformity of size and all damaged seeds were discarded. Before the bioassay seeds were washed with tap water and the surface were sterilized using NaCl (10% v/v) for 10 min followed by several washes in sterile distilled water. For

testing phytotoxicity dehydrated ethanol was used as control. Bioassays were carried out using petridishes (90 mm diameter) containing a sheet of Whatman 1 filter paper as support. Test solutions (5 ml) was added to the filter paper in the petridish and dried completely *in vacuo* at 40 °C. Five seeds from each category were placed on the filter paper and incubated for 7 days at 25 °C in the dark. The effects of the pure compounds were determined by measuring the elongation of roots and average for each concentration.

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